

Appendix S1: Climatic data and main survey information

Fractal sampling design reveals climate and scale effects on rainforest bird communities in central Africa

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Appendix S1 summarizes the climatic datasets and field survey details used in this study. It includes site-specific rainfall and temperature data derived from multiple climate products, the temporal distribution of sampling across the rainfall gradient, and the composition of detection types across forest sites.

FIGURE S1 Profile of the rainfall gradient.

Dashed lines indicate mean values per climatic product, black line indicate mean values of the four climatic products.

TABLE S1: Summary of climatic variables used in the present study.

Gradient strata	Dataset	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Campo	CHELSA	Rainfall	3,077.7	25.2	3,026.6	3,113.1
Campo	CHELSA	Temperature	24.8	0.1	24.8	24.9
Campo	CHIRPS	Rainfall	2,315.5	23.5	2,282.7	2,331.9
Campo	CRU	Rainfall	2,549.5	0.0	2,549.5	2,549.5
Campo	WorldClim	Rainfall	2,320.2	7.0	2,303.0	2,323.0
Campo	WorldClim	Temperature	25.3	0.0	25.2	25.3
Dja	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,490.3	6.7	1,477.4	1,503.8
Dja	CHELSA	Temperature	23.5	0.1	23.4	23.6
Dja	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,581.2	3.3	1,579.7	1,588.4
Dja	CRU	Rainfall	1,554.6	0.0	1,554.6	1,554.6
Dja	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,606.8	1.5	1,602.0	1,608.0
Dja	WorldClim	Temperature	23.7	0.0	23.7	23.8
Lobeke	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,468.5	15.8	1,446.6	1,494.7
Lobeke	CHELSA	Temperature	24.5	0.0	24.4	24.6
Lobeke	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,596.3	7.3	1,592.4	1,609.8
Lobeke	CRU	Rainfall	1,655.2	0.0	1,655.2	1,655.2
Lobeke	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,579.0	0.0	1,579.0	1,579.0
Lobeke	WorldClim	Temperature	24.7	0.0	24.7	24.7
Mbam et Djerem	CHELSA	Rainfall	1,837.7	21.3	1,795.2	1,873.0
Mbam et Djerem	CHELSA	Temperature	23.8	0.1	23.6	24.0
Mbam et Djerem	CHIRPS	Rainfall	1,740.2	11.4	1,734.2	1,761.2
Mbam et Djerem	CRU	Rainfall	1,562.8	27.9	1,548.1	1,614.3
Mbam et Djerem	WorldClim	Rainfall	1,605.7	2.9	1,603.0	1,612.0
Mbam et Djerem	WorldClim	Temperature	23.3	0.1	23.2	23.5

TABLE S2: Schedule of sampling across the gradient.

All locations were sampled during the Dry season (highest activity peak) and transitions to the wet season, ensuring covering both seasons and the peak of activity. Survey time indicated the time expended deploying the gamma fractals and doing the point count surveys.

Gradient strata	season	Time period	Surveys time
Campo Mann	Dry and early wet seasons	July-August 2023	52 days
Lobeke	Dry and late wet season	November -December 2023	50 days
Mbam et Djerem	Dry and early wet seasons	July-August 2024	54 days
Dja	Dry and early wet season	March-April 2024	49 days

Note: Due to distance among locations (> 300 km), the fact that surveys were done by a single ornithologist and the difficult access to the points, sampling dates (months) differed but all covered the dry season and at least one transition to the wet season.

TABLE S3 Taxonomic overlap among sites.

Level	shared	total	Shared
Order	10	15	66.6
Families	32	42	76.1
Genus	59	106	55.6
Species	68	175	38.8

Note: Shared species are defined as those recorded at all four forest sites

TABLE S4 Top 20 bird species by number of point-count detections

Rank	Scientific name	Number of detections
1	<i>Eurillas virens</i>	587
2	<i>Eurillas latirostris</i>	531
3	<i>Cyanomitra olivacea</i>	485
4	<i>Pogoniulus subsulphureus</i>	440
5	<i>Ceratogymna atrata</i>	332
6	<i>Oriolus brachyrynchus</i>	297
7	<i>Hylia prasina</i>	263
8	<i>Apalis rufogularis</i>	251
9	<i>Nicator chloris</i>	245
10	<i>Bleda syndactylus</i>	227
11	<i>Nicator vireo</i>	226
12	<i>Psittacus erithacus</i>	223
13	<i>Platysteira castanea</i>	190
14	<i>Macrosphenus flavicans</i>	189

15	<i>Pogoniulus scolopaceus</i>	180
16	<i>Macrosphenus concolor</i>	177
17	<i>Criniger calurus</i>	169
18	<i>Camaroptera supercilialis</i>	160
19	<i>Camaroptera chloronota</i>	158
20	<i>Cyanomitra cyanolaema</i>	155

TABLE S5 Detection distance summary by site

Site	Numbers with distance	Within 50m
Lobeke	2320	83.9
Dja	2875	78.4
Mbam	2979	74.1
Campo	2415	64.3

TABLE S6 Detection mode

Mode	Total	%
auditory	10118	95.55
visual	470	4.43

Table S7. Site summary richness, raw abundance, singletons and doubletons

Site	N species	Total individuals	N singletons	N doubletons
Campo	107	1624	10	14
Dja	118	1901	18	10
Lobeke	120	1982	20	9
Mbam	123	1767	17	13

FIGURE S2: Number of species per family across the rainfall gradient

Note: Taxonomy followed was Clements/ebird taxonomy

FIGURE S3: Total number of individuals per species across the rainfall gradient (raw data)

Note: Taxonomy followed was Clements/ebird taxonomy

